

ANALYSIS OF MULTIAXIAL CYCLIC STRESS STATE IN A WIND TURBINE BLADE

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ABSTRACT

An approach is proposed to investigate multiaxial cyclic stress states in non crimp fabrics wind turbine blade plies and laminate during a blade normal rotation. Observations show two trends at the laminate scale depending on the presence of 0° plies. Stress state is mainly uniaxial for laminates containing 0° plies, but multiaxial where laminate skins contain only $\pm 45^\circ$ plies with a shear stress component that can exceed axial one in several areas. At ply scale, 0° plies are under uniaxial stress state whereas high multiaxial stress states are observed in off-axis plies which justify studying effect of stress state multiaxiality on fatigue damage in wind turbine blades. Multiaxial results taken from literature show that shear stress has a huge impact on the fatigue life which is not highlighted by the Puck criterion.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today, wind turbine blade market is focussed on offshore where blades need to be even more efficient than onshore ones to make offshore wind farm cost effective [1]. A way to improve blades efficiency is to improve composite design against fatigue [2]. Indeed, because of the lack of a cumulative fatigue damage rule unanimously recognized for composite laminates under complex stress state, blade designers have to choose between very heavy testing campaigns carried out on all laminate lay-ups present in the blade or apply conservative laws [3].

Scientific community works on the improvement of composite laminates fatigue life assessment methods for many years, and a lot of models are proposed in literature among which ply scale damage models seems attractive for their ability to predict stiffness and strength losses cycles after cycles for any laminate.

The work presented here is the first part of an approach which aims to identify a damage model formulated at the ply scale and being able to describe both fatigue residual strength and stiffness in wind turbine blades. Shear and transverse stresses are known to decrease fatigue properties of laminates generally loaded in fibre direction. Therefore, quantifying shear and transverse stress is the essential preliminary job to carry out before to try to compute fatigue damage in the blade.

A methodology is proposed hereafter to determine the cyclic multiaxial fatigue stress state at the ply scale. Representative parameters of the multiaxial stress state will be defined and applied to composite in-plane stress components computed from a composite shell finite element model. Main multiaxial stress state will be underlined at laminate and ply scales and we will try to extract critical stress states using the quasi-static Puck criterion and literature experimental results.

2 PRELIMINARY DEFINITIONS

2.1 Non crimp fabrics

Laminates in wind turbine blades are composed by non crimp fabrics (NCF). This dry fibre reinforcement consists in several unidirectional layers, stacked in different orientations and stitched together by a stitching yarn.

NCF have advantage to accelerate ply laying in the mould and to have better mechanical properties than woven plies under quasi-static [4] and fatigue [5] loading. Let us remark that NCF elastic plies behaviour is accurately predicted under static loading by classical thin laminate theory [6]. Each ply can be modelled as a unidirectional ply.

2.2 In plane stress state and coordinate systems

Stress states in composite laminate is analysed hereafter at two scales: laminate and ply scale. Laminate and ply stresses are defined respectively in (x,y,z) and (x_1,x_2,x_3) coordinate system. The laminate coordinate system is defined with x aligned with the blade pitch axis toward blade tip, z normal to the shell oriented inside the blade, and y the complementary so that x, y, z rotate clockwise. The NCF ply coordinate system is defined with axis x_1 aligned with fibres, axis x_2 perpendicular to fibres so that x_1, x_2, x_3 rotate clockwise, axis x_3 is equivalent to axis z of the laminate (Fig. 1)

Figure 1 : Coordinates systems considered

According to the classical laminate theory, external cyclic forces acting on the blade: gravity, accelerations and aerodynamic pressure, create a plane stress state acting on the laminate in an elementary volume (Fig.1). We assume that the laminate stress components follow a synchronous sinusoidal time evolution (Eq.1):

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_x(t) = \sigma_{x,m} + \sigma_{x,a} \sin(\omega t) \\ \sigma_y(t) = \sigma_{y,m} + \sigma_{y,a} \sin(\omega t - \phi_{y,x}) \\ \tau_{xy}(t) = \tau_{xy,m} + \tau_{xy,a} \sin(\omega t - \phi_{xy,x}) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where subscripts m and a denote respectively the mean stress and the amplitude, ω is the angular velocity, and $\phi_{y,x}$ and $\phi_{xy,x}$ are the phase shifts between $\sigma_y(t)$ and $\sigma_x(t)$ and between $\tau_{xy}(t)$ and $\sigma_x(t)$ respectively. Consequently, one can demonstrate that stress components at the ply scale can be written in a similar form:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_1(t) = \sigma_{1,m} + \sigma_{1,a} \sin(\omega t) \\ \sigma_2(t) = \sigma_{2,m} + \sigma_{2,a} \sin(\omega t - \phi_{2,1}) \\ \sigma_6(t) = \sigma_{6,m} + \sigma_{6,a} \sin(\omega t - \phi_{6,1}) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where, similarly to Eq. (1), subscripts m and a refer respectively to mean stress and to amplitude, and $\phi_{2,1}$ and $\phi_{6,1}$ are the phase shifts between $\sigma_2(t)$ and $\sigma_1(t)$ and between $\sigma_6(t)$ and $\sigma_1(t)$ respectively.

2.3 Principal stress axis orientation

A way to understand the whole multiaxial stress state is to compute the principal stress axis orientation given by Eq. (3).

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{atan}\left(\frac{2\tau_{xy}}{\sigma_x - \sigma_y}\right) \text{ or } \theta = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{atan}\left(\frac{2\tau_6}{\sigma_1 - \sigma_2}\right) \quad (3)$$

The principal stress axis orientation θ , defined in (3), can be computed at laminate or ply scale and varies between -45 and +45 degrees. It gives the angle between x-axis, or fibre axis, and the nearest axis of the principal stress coordinate system.

The principal stress axis orientation may be different at each loading time step. Therefore, we will analyse the whole cycle considering mean and amplitude values defined by Eq. (4) and (5):

$$\theta_{mean} = \frac{\theta_{max} + \theta_{min}}{2} \quad (4)$$

$$\theta_{amplitude} = \frac{\theta_{max} - \theta_{min}}{2} \quad (5)$$

where θ_{max} and θ_{min} are the maximum and minimum values of the principal stress axis orientation during a cycle. The mean value of the principal stress axis orientation gives information about the presence of static shear in the stress state; whereas the principal stress axis orientation amplitude gives information about proportionality of stressing.

2.4 Representative parameters of the biaxial stress state

In order to deepen analysis, multiaxiality of the in-plane stress state at the laminate, or at the ply scale, will be analysed in terms of biaxiality. The following parameters are studied, two components per two components, in order to appreciate the biaxial cyclic stress state whose graphic interpretation is proposed in Fig. 2.

The first parameter studied is the fatigue biaxial ratio defined, as proposed by M. Quaresimin et al. in [7], as the ratio of amplitudes (Eq. 6):

$$\lambda_{ij} = \frac{\sigma_{i,a}}{\sigma_{j,a}} \quad (6)$$

where i and j correspond to stress directions.

In order to avoid the analysis of values being able to approach infinity, we work with angles rather than slopes (Eq.7):

$$\alpha_i = \text{atan}(\lambda_i) \quad (7)$$

The second parameter used is static biaxial ratio defined as the ratio of mean stresses (Eq. 8).

$$\gamma_{ij} = \frac{\sigma_{i,m}}{\sigma_{j,m}} \quad (8)$$

Same remark than for the first parameter, we use an angle rather than a slope to display results (Eq.9).

$$\beta_i = \text{atan}(\gamma_i) \quad (9)$$

The third parameter that can be studied is the phase shift between components. This parameter is interesting in order to understand the loading chronology the material sees and proportionality between components.

The fourth parameter: ellipse opening is displayed to give a better idea of the proportionality between the components studied. Of course the information of proportionality is already available with the phase shift but ellipse opening provides a very visual and easy-to-understand result. Ellipse opening, defined as the ratio of short axis versus long axis can be computed from phase shift [8] (Eq.10).

$$\left(\frac{b}{a}\right)_{ij} = \sqrt{\frac{(1 + \lambda_{ij}^2) \sqrt{(1 - \lambda_{ij}^2)^2 + 4 \cdot \lambda_{ij}^2 \cdot \cos^2 \phi_{i,j}} - (1 - \lambda_{ij}^2)^2 - 4 \cdot \lambda_{ij}^2 \cdot \cos^2 \phi_{i,j}}{(1 + \lambda_{ij}^2) \sqrt{(1 - \lambda_{ij}^2)^2 + 4 \cdot \lambda_{ij}^2 \cdot \cos^2 \phi_{i,j}} + (1 - \lambda_{ij}^2)^2 + 4 \cdot \lambda_{ij}^2 \cdot \cos^2 \phi_{i,j}}} \quad (10)$$

Figure 2 : Useful parameters to identify a biaxial cyclic stress state

3 MULTIAXIAL STRESS STATE ANALYSIS IN A WIND TURBINE BLADE

3.1 Wind turbine blade and loading

The multiaxial parameters presented in the previous section have been used to study the multiaxial stress state in a 23 meter wind turbine blade. This blade is a modern stall controlled carbon and glass-epoxy blade designed by Tensyl Company, and certified by DNV-GL the 17th of March 2015 in the frame of EFFIWIND project. A narrow carbon-epoxy main spar cap and an unidirectional glass-epoxy second stiffener near trailing edge and leading and trailing edge reinforcement sustain bending loads whereas torsion and shear are recovered by the $\pm 45^\circ$ reinforced glass-epoxy shells and shear webs (Fig. 3). A core material is introduced in shells and shear webs to avoid buckling. Therefore blade laminate scantling is often a sandwich. However, in the following, stress state is studied in skins only.

The loading situation studied here is a rotation of the blade under normal wind profile [3,9] which assume that wind speed vary versus altitude according a power law. A wind velocity of 20 m/s at hub height of 46 meters above ground and a normal power law exponent of 0.2 are considered.

During one rotation at constant speed:

- Gravity applies a sinusoidal load due to its oscillating direction between chord and pitch axis.
- Centrifugal acceleration applies a constant force depending only on the position along the blade.
- Wind pressure applies a varying force according to the passage in front of the tower and to the variation of the attack angle (depending on the wind speed gradient between upward and downward blade position).

A dynamic aeroelastic simulation has been achieved with FAST [10] software developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory. Loads are then applied in a composite shell element model. Stresses at each ply and equivalent stresses at laminate scale are computed with the finite element code NASTRAN by linear static analysis according to classical laminate theory. Material elastic properties of table 1 are considered.

Finally, parameters defined in section 2.3 and 2.4 are computed for the whole laminate and each unidirectional glass-epoxy ply oriented at 0° , $+45^\circ$ and -45° compared to the blade pitch axis.

Figure 3: Distribution of materials in the blade.

	V_f [%]	E_1 [MPa]	E_2 [MPa]	G_{12} [MPa]	ν_{12} [-]
UD glass-epoxy	50%	39405	9033	3485	0.3

Table 1: Material in plane elastic properties

3.2 Principal stress axis orientation

The principal stress axis orientation is computed at each time step of the blade rotation at the laminate and ply level. Then, maximum and minimum angles are extracted, mean and amplitude values are computed for each element composing the blade according to Eq. 4 and 5. The distributions of mean and amplitude values over the blade are displayed in Fig. 4 for the laminate scale (in green for $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates and in red for $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates) and Fig. 5 for the ply scale (in blue, green and red for respectively $+45^\circ$, -45° and 0° plies). Histograms of each kind of laminate or ply are normalized and stacked to provide an easier analysis.

Figure 4: Laminate scale – Principal stress axis mean and amplitude distribution

Figure 5: Ply scale – Principal stress axis mean and amplitude distribution

At the laminate scale, (Fig.4) two trends are observed. The first trend concerns $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates. In these laminates, the principal stress axis mean and amplitude angle distributions are concentrated around 0° . It means that shear stress is very low in the stress state and stressing is mainly proportional. The second trend concerns $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates. In these laminates, principal stress axis mean angle takes all values between -45° and $+45^\circ$ (Fig.4.a). It means that shear stress is often present in the stress state. The principal stress axis amplitude distribution shows (Fig 4.b) that stressing aims to be proportional. However non proportionality can reach a variation of 15° in amplitude of principal stress coordinate system during a blade rotation.

At the ply scale (Fig.5.), the same kind of analysis distinguishes two trends. The first trend is one of 0° plies, in which shear stress seems very low (Fig.5.a) and stressing is proportional (Fig.5.b). The second trend is one of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, where principal stress axis are directed at 16° from fibre for most elements, but can take all directions (Fig.5.a). It means that shear stress is very high in these plies. In $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, non proportionality is higher than for 0° plies (Fig.5.b).

3.3 Biaxial analysis

Distribution of the four biaxial parameters defined in section 2.4 are computed for geometrical stress components at the laminate level, over all composite shell elements within the blade, and displayed in Fig. 6 and 7, in green for $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates and in red for $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates. Analysis is restricted here to shear and transverse stresses versus axial stress because these stress components are known to decrease fatigue properties in fibre direction and therefore to have an impact on the fatigue life of the blade. Histograms of each kind of laminate are normalized and stacked. Analysis of these parameters shows interesting results and two trends can be distinguished.

The first trend is one laminates containing axial reinforcements (carbon or glass plies oriented at 0°). These laminates sustain mainly a unidirectional stress state. Transverse and shear geometrical stresses are negligible compared to axial ones (Fig. 6. and 7. - red histogram).

The second trend, more interesting in terms of multiaxial stressing is related to [±45°] laminates. Static biaxial angle distribution shows that the blade is subjected to a static or a mean stress mainly directed along x direction (Fig. 6.b. and 7.b.), due to centrifugal acceleration. However, transverse stress is not negligible (Fig. 6.b.) and shear static stress became greater than axial stress for some elements of laminates (Fig. 7.b.).

Around this mean stress - we have just described using the static biaxial angle β - [±45°] laminates are subjected to alternating components described by the fatigue biaxial angle α . Proportion of axial stress amplitude is greater than transverse stress amplitude (Fig. 6.a) but transverse cyclic stress is not negligible. Regarding biaxiality of shear versus axial stress, proportion of shear stress amplitude can equal axial stress amplitude or even be greater (Fig. 7.a.). Stress state is mainly proportional in [±45°] laminates (Fig. 6.c, 6.d, 7.c, and 7.d.). However phase shift became important for some [±45°] laminate elements of skins.

Figure 6: Laminate scale – Biaxiality of σ_y versus σ_x

Figure 7: Laminate scale – Biaxiality of τ_{xy} versus σ_x

The same methodology of analysis can be carried out for each unidirectional ply whose multiaxial parameter distributions are stacked in Fig. 8 for biaxiality of σ_2 versus σ_1 and Fig. 9 for biaxiality of σ_6 versus σ_1 .

We may begin to analyze plies at 0° which appear in red in graphs. Unidirectional plies orientated in the blade longitudinal axis sustain a unidirectional fatigue stress. In these plies, transverse and shear stress are almost negligible when compared to stress carried out by fibres. (Fig. 8.a, 8.b, 9.a, 9.b). When we look at the results concerning ±45° plies, in blue and green in graphs, it appears that the principal stress direction is orientated at about 16° from fibre direction (Fig. 8.a and 8.b) as observed

in Fig. 5 of the previous section. Therefore, most of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies are stressed with transverse or shear stresses about 30% (α or $\beta = 16^\circ$) in range and mean value of stress in fibre direction. This proportion can reach 175% in the tail of distribution (α or $\beta = 60^\circ$) (Fig. 8.a, 8.b, 9.a. and 9.b.).

Figure 8: Glass-epoxy ply scale – Biaxiality of σ_2 versus σ_1

Figure 9: Glass-epoxy ply scale – Biaxiality of σ_6 versus σ_1

Reader may have noticed that biaxiality in carbon plies of the main spar cap had not been presented. Indeed, the higher carbon stiffness compared with glass in fibre direction make its loading even more unidirectional and fatigue strength of the product used make these plies less critical regarding fatigue strength. However, laminates containing carbon plies and $\pm 45^\circ$ shell glass plies surrounding carbon are included in the results in order to take into account the effect of carbon fibres in the behaviour of surrounding plies.

3.4 Preliminary conclusion

The following conclusions can be drawn out from our results. At the laminate scale the stress state is mainly uniaxial for $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates but not for $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates where transverse stress is not negligible and shear stress can exceed axial one. Therefore, assumption to consider only unidirectional fatigue in blade skin to compute blade fatigue life [3] seems validated for $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates but not for $[\pm 45^\circ]$ ones.

At ply scale, on-axis plies are uniaxially stressed whereas off-axis plies sustain a high degree of multi-axiality. In off-axis plies, orientated at $\pm 45^\circ$ in this blade, for most elements, principal stress coordinate system is orientated at 16° from fibre direction which lead to transverse and shear stresses of 30% of stresses in fibre direction. However, results have shown that principal stress coordinate system can be orientated in all direction and generate stress states with shear or transverse stresses of 175% of fibre stress.

Attention of the reader must be drawn on the fact that these results depend on blade design, material mechanical properties, loading configuration and loads introduction method in the finite

element model. In this paper, the studied design situation does not take into account the whole load spectrum a blade is likely to sustain during its life and complementary simulations should be necessary to take into account stress states related to start or stop procedures for example, or any other specific wind and working condition.

A special care must also be taken when results are interpreted because we are speaking about stress states of non isotropic materials. Therefore, shear and transverse strength are lower than axial one and a low stress multiaxial degree can be very critical for the material.

4 CRITICAL MULTIAXIAL STRESS STATES

Knowing multiaxial stress state in each ply of the blade is a good beginning. Nevertheless, it does not say which one is critical.

4.1 Experimental observations

A comparison of experimental data taken from literature [7] focuses on the effect of multiaxial stress state at ply scale on the fatigue life. Authors conclude that the fatigue biaxial ratio λ_{21} has a huge impact on fatigue life in fibre direction. However, λ_{61} does not seem critical and experimental results about phase shifts ϕ are not conclusive. In one case phase shift increase fatigue life and in another case phase shift decreases the fatigue life. In a complementary study [11], the authors show that transverse fatigue life decrease when λ_{62} increases. Indeed, it seems that shear stress damages plies causing decohesion between matrix and fibre which penalise stress repartition between fibre and decrease fatigue strength in fibre directions.

4.2 Computation of Puck criterion

An interesting criterion taking into account shear stress influence on ply strength is the Puck one [12]. Furthermore, this criterion is the recommended criterion [3] to investigate unidirectional plies strength under multiaxial stress states in wind turbine blades. It is a static criterion and therefore a priori not adapted to investigate the fatigue strength. However, it gives an idea of the most critical stress state met during the cycle. Puck failure index is given by Eq. 11 in fibre direction and Eq. 12 in matrix direction.

$$\begin{cases} f_E = \frac{\sigma_1}{R_{//}^{(+)}} & \text{for } \sigma_1 \geq 0 \\ f_E = \frac{\sigma_1}{-R_{//}^{(-)}} & \text{for } \sigma_1 < 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{cases} f_E = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\tau_{21}}{R_{//}}\right)^2 + \left(1 - p_{\perp}^{(+)} \cdot \frac{R_{\perp}^{(+)}}{R_{//}}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{R_{\perp}^{(+)}}\right)^2} + p_{\perp}^{(+)} \cdot \frac{\sigma_2}{R_{//}} & \text{if } \sigma_2 \geq 0 \\ f_E = \frac{1}{R_{//}} \left(\sqrt{\tau_{21}^2 + (p_{\perp}^{(-)} \sigma_2)^2} + p_{\perp}^{(-)} \sigma_2 \right) & \text{if } \sigma_2 < 0 \text{ and } \left| \frac{\tau_{21}}{\sigma_2} \right| \geq \frac{|\tau_{21c}|}{R_{\perp}^A} \\ f_E = \left[\left(\frac{\tau_{21}}{2(R_{//} + p_{\perp}^{(-)} R_{\perp}^A)} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{R_{\perp}^{(-)}} \right)^2 \right] \frac{R_{\perp}^{(-)}}{-\sigma_2} & \text{if } \sigma_2 < 0 \text{ and } \left| \frac{\tau_{21}}{\sigma_2} \right| \leq \frac{|\tau_{21c}|}{R_{\perp}^A} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $R_{//}^{(+)}, R_{//}^{(-)}, R_{\perp}^{(+)}, R_{\perp}^{(-)}, R_{//}$ are respectively the fibre tensile, fibre compressive, transverse tensile, transverse compressive and in-plane shear strengths, $p_{\perp}^{(+)}$ and $p_{\perp}^{(-)}$ are the Puck inclination parameter [12] and τ_{21c} and R_{\perp}^A are given by Eq. 13 and 14.

$$\tau_{21c} = R_{\perp//} \cdot \sqrt{1 + 2 \cdot p_{\perp}^{(-)} \frac{R_{\perp\perp}^A}{R_{\perp//}}} \quad (13)$$

$$R_{\perp\perp}^A = \frac{R_{\perp//}}{2p_{\perp}^{(-)}} \left(\sqrt{1 + 2p_{\perp}^{(-)} \frac{R_{\perp\perp}^{(-)}}{R_{\perp//}}} - 1 \right) \quad (14)$$

Thus, Puck criterion [12] was computed for all the plies at each time step of the blade rotation, and the maximum failure index, from fibre or matrix directions, over the cycle is extracted and plotted, in Fig. 10 to 12, regarding the multiaxial parameters defined in sections 2.3 and 2.4. Material data of tables 1 and 2 are considered. When the failure index tends to 0, stress state is not dangerous for the structure and a failure index upper than 1 means a failure regarding this criterion.

Apart from some points with high Puck failure index, due to model singularities, among stress states at the ply scale present in the blade for the rotation investigated, no stress state seems to be identified as more critical than other regarding Puck criterion. In most cases, we may even say that a same stress state may generate a Puck failure index varying from 0 to 0.5.

Figure 10: Maximum Puck failure index regarding principal stress axis orientation

Figure 11: Maximum Puck failure index regarding biaxial parameters of σ_2 versus σ_1

Figure 12: Maximum Puck failure index regarding biaxial parameters of σ_6 versus σ_1

However it can be interesting to note that the maximum values of the Puck failure index are observed for $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. It means that these plies will be probably damaged before 0° plies and then this will modify the stress state. Indeed, attention of the reader has to be drawn here on the fact that initial elastic properties are considered in a static criterion. In order to really study critical fatigue stress state, a fatigue criterion should be used considering damaged properties of the plies. However, even if such criteria exist they are not very accurate [7].

	$R_{//}^{(+)}$	$R_{//}^{(-)}$	$R_{\perp}^{(+)}$	$R_{\perp}^{(-)}$	$R_{\perp//}$	$p_{\perp}^{(+)}$	$p_{\perp}^{(-)}$
	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[-]	[-]
UD glass-epoxy	591	532	45	135	52	0.30	0.25

Table 2: Material in plane strength properties

5 CONCLUSIONS

A methodology for multiaxial stress state investigation has been proposed: two multiaxial fatigue parameters and four biaxial fatigue parameters were defined and applied on real medium wind turbine blade simulation results, at laminate and NCF ply scale, for one blade nominal rotation.

At the laminate scale, two behaviours are observed depending on the presence of 0° plies. Stress state is mainly uniaxial for $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates. However, a multiaxial state is observed for $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates with a shear component which can exceed axial one in specific location like shear webs.

At the ply scale, 0° plies are uniaxially stressed. However, the principal stress coordinate system of off-axis plies is orientated for most elements at 16° from fibre direction which leads to biaxial stress state with ratio of transverse or shear stress versus axial component of 30%. Other principal stress axis observed can induce biaxial ratio of up to 175%.

According to literature results, shear stress, often present in the blade laminate stress state, seems to induce damage in unidirectional plies and decrease fatigue life in fibre and matrix directions. However, the criteria applied to find critical stress states was not conclusive and an additional effort should be done in this way by applying for example multiaxial fatigue criteria.

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